

The Problem of Power and Management in the Information Society

Shattyk Aliyev, Zhakypbek Altayev, Pirimbek Suleimenov, Asset Kuranbek, and Zhamila Amirkulova

Abstract—Modern civilization has come in recent decades into a new phase in its development, called the information society. The concept of "information society" has become one of the most common. Therefore, the attempt to understand what exactly the society we live in, what are its essential features, and possible future scenarios, is important to the social and philosophical analysis.

At the heart of all these deep transformations is more increasing, almost defining role knowledge and information as play substrata of «information society». The mankind opened for itself and actively exploits a new resource – information. Information society puts forward on the arena new type of the power, at the heart of which activity – mastering by a new resource: information and knowledge. The password of the new power – intelligence as synthesis of knowledge, information and communications, the strength of mind, fundamental sociocultural values. In a postindustrial society, the power of knowledge and information is crucial in the management of the company, pushing into the background the influence of money and state coercion.

Keywords—Information society, philosophy of power, management, globalization and innovation.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN today's rapidly changing world, when the eyes of several generations at the same time there is a change and transformation of socio-cultural and civilizational foundations of human existence, value system, ideology and worldview, it becomes especially important issue of cultural adaptation and socialization strategies. XXI century is the age of information, mankind has stepped a new level of development. This level of development is the informational society. Scientists give a lot of definitions of time that we are witnessing. The first call it as "the age of globalization," the second as a "post-modern", others "informational" society. But one thing is, we live in an informational society based on the "information explosion." We wish it or not, but the flow of time as we see.

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The high-speed Internet penetration, satellite, audio and video show us the growth of technological innovation of the globalized world. These processes have a strong effect on the formation and change of consciousness. In this case, it's very important for the citizens to be informational literate. Therefore, understanding the kind of society we live in, and how impacts it is - our first responsibility.

As well, new manager relationships establish new cultural forms of the information society, which affect the political mechanisms. This is media culture, information culture, net culture, etc.

The XXI century was not only the age of information but also the age of psychology. When it was discovered that human mind can be susceptible to convincement, information in the form of propaganda became a major instrument for controlling people. It gradually replaced force and violence, which have long been considered the sole and indispensable governing tools.

The modern political power takes on a new resource, absent in earlier historical periods of social development - information and communication resource of the ideological impact of the media and the Internet on the individual and society. The acceleration of change and constant innovation require a new form of political power, new forms of government and new political leaders. Information networks are transforming all areas and shifting power structures. This will require new styles of leadership – overcoming the one-sidedness, organization of creative political leadership.

Investigation of the relationship with the power of media is to consider the question of what power is. And not only that in the last half century has radically changed the understanding of power in the social sciences and humanities, and there are new concepts of power, but that the institution of government has changed drastically, along with changes in society over the past fifty years. And mass communication have made a significant contribution to these changes, therefore, the institute authorities.

Means of communication were always crucial sources for ideological impact on the society and the distribution of its powerful impact on the culture. For example, developing of writing system brought changes in the political structure, of the society and developed an opportunity of creating massive, controlled by writing, governments and empires. Huge opportunities for media exposure of the active political consciousness and citizens' behavior indicates the crucial role of the "fourth estate (power) in modern society. Some researchers even say, Mass Communications of the coming era of "mediacracy" - government media, do not reflect and

interpret reality as by its own rules and discretion.

The modern political manager gradually got rid of the old ways and adopted a new form. For today the political manager gained new ideological, informational and communicative resources with the media and the Internet, which greatly affect the individual and society. Speedy change of time and innovations that appear almost every day, require new types of political rule and authority. Networks entangle all industries and political structure with each other.

The idea of the "information society" first appeared in the late 60's - early 70's of the last century, whose founders are D. Bell and O. Toffler. They believed that after the agricultural and the industrial era of human civilization will come the information age. Researchers justify the concept of the information society by such evidence that "technological innovations engender fundamentally cultural and social change, and the world will be totally different."

The researchers emphasize that the term "global information society", from the political, economic, cultural and social point of view, is the concept of "scale-information industry, developing by increasing of information and knowledge." This phenomenon is closely linked to the emergence of global computer networks, and above all, the Internet. Appearance of them and liberalization of market all over the world, reduction in price of communication services are two factors of increasing of informational sector and its social role.

Lots of foreign scientists as Y. Masuda, A. Toffler, G. Bechmann, D. Bell, A. Acker, B. Hakk, B. Louder, A. Macintosh worked on informational society theory and world experience of electronic society theory.

The relevance of the research topic is due to the complexity and ambiguity of the realities of post-industrialism, the urgent need for social and philosophical analysis of social transformation in a rapidly changing information society. Transformation of control and power is an inevitable process. According A. Toffler: "... We are entering an era of metamorphosis power. We live in a time when the entire power structure, held together by a world disintegrates. A completely different structure takes the form " [1].

Most important in culture of management are rational beginning, education, modern concepts and scientific technologies. It's very difficult to make reforms and control the state correctly without education nowadays. People have to get informed, and of course it is not dangerous for state. If the information come timely and fully, that will be useful for state and people.

Nowadays the problem of management, which is based on information, didn't lose its topicality. Maybe it will take new speed and express itself in the future.

Everyone know that English word "management" takes beginning from Latin word "manus", which means "hand". At the beginning it meant "to control animals". Then it took another meaning, this time in spheres connected to people. Management means to gain the goals, organizing social responsibility which is based to get useful results. Management is determined by recognizing the aim of special

control, suggesting new areas, also by the level of control based on mind and intellect. The management process will not be useful without using innovational aim, responsibility and special methods. Actually, there are four function of management: planning, organization, motivation and observing. The question of personal management is becoming one of the actual questions nowadays. Human factor must stay at the heart of any control action. For example, Japanese management. Japanese management consists of classic European management culture and Japanese conventionality. They made their own conception. All of the new technologies are based to wake people's motivation to work. Japanese industry is made for agreement and safety of worker. This kind of organization of industry is more profitable than Americans', who make more attention on technical side.

Management has several meanings in informational society:

- 1) Management as social and economical institute that affects to social opinion, politics and culture, entrepreneurship actions.
- 2) Group of people who administer in spiritual industry and media production spheres (newspapers, magazines, books, movies, TV shows, DVD, CD).
- 3) Production of information, using processes, technically organization of media and social-economical.

Political power uses several tools to materialize in society. They are called power's resources in scientific literature. Power's resources are divided in such types as:

- 1) Economical (material needs);
- 2) Social (tools that are intended to change status);
- 3) Force resources (army, police, weapons);
- 4) Informational (education and informational tools);
- 5) Demographical (human – main social tool).

According to A. Toffler's opinion education and informational tools are very significant from all other tools nowadays.

New kind of power, which is based on information and education, is increasing in informational society. The main features of new power are intellect as a synthesis of education, information and communication, spiritual power of social-cultural valuables. More society becomes intellectual, more difficult to manage it without making attention to psychological features.

Methods of communication have always been an important means of ideological influence on people and the distribution of power relations in culture. For example, the invention of writing led to a change in society and political system, created the possibility of creating large, managed by the letter, states and empires. Contemporary Media coincidence is called "fourth estate", but the degree of influence and impact on people, they should be called the "first" because in modern societies, they act much more effectively and efficiently than direct political and legal coercion. Tactics of power and effect of media is much thinner, more delicate and refined than that of political power, so it is much harder to detect and avoid.

The question of the power we are interested not in itself (not as a political science problem), but primarily as it relates to media communications. "Bridge" connecting the

communication with the authorities, is an ideology. Media Communication implements a power function does not directly force (as the state apparatus, government agencies or the "power structures") and through ideology, ideological apparatus. "Ideology as a system of ideas - says James Lull, - has a persuasive force when such ideas can be submitted and presented in the communication. Then it is natural that the media and all other major social institutions play a crucial role in the dissemination of ideologies. Fabricators become the dominant ideologies of the "information elite." Their power and dominance stems directly from their ability to publicly articulate their preferred system of ideas. Ironically, in today's world many of the social "elite group" should depend on the non-elite cultural forms - the mass media and popular culture - in the circulation of their ideologies to maintain their high social status" [2].

Authority is an institution rather than direct political violence and coercion. It is an institute of cultural hegemony. In Gramsci's theory terms, it is the institute of cultural superiority, which creates conditions for political and legal power. Before the conquest of political power, Gramsci wrote, the class that claims domination has to create a new system of values and make it dominant, ie win the hearts and minds of people, and only on this basis, claim to political hegemony. Preceded by a cultural hegemony of the political. Only such an understanding helps to clarify the power of power and ideological functions of government. Media Communication provides the power of the methods of "natural representation" and the annoying repetition, rather than coercion and threats, and that is why these forms of power are more efficient.

It's considered that information is one of the resources of management, such as human, material resources. Information is becoming a strategic importance in a new developing civilization. Manufacture and consumption of information is becoming a base of development in all spheres of social life and profitable management.

Informing became a global inexhaustible source of humanity; we stepped to endless information's power era. Management has incredible power in this era. Informing, managing and organizing are like a big locomotive that leads us to progress. Also, they are important in development of states.

The rapid spread of printing throughout Europe has been one of the greatest cultural revolutions in human history, which affected not only the scope of the press and media, but also more fundamental social and cultural institutions - from the institution of government (state) economy, and to religious and ethnic relations. Even Francis Bacon said that the printing press changed the "look and condition of the world." The book was both a product of mass and rapid (instantaneous) consumption - the two main qualities that shaped the market economy. Grassroots Books was founded in the principle of the printing press, it was mass made cheap and accessible book. However the book itself is radically affected the level of human consciousness and culture.

If we take the "little sister" of the book - a newspaper, then there are two important features - mass - appears even

brighter. The newspaper, in contrast to the book, intended for "general reader", originally intended for immediate consumption. Yesterday's newspaper today, already out of date, no one comes to mind (except for special cases) read the newspaper last year. As aptly observes Hegel in one of his aphorisms, a newspaper for modern man is a "morning prayer" citizen. The newspaper - it is a religion of a man, a ritual which is performed at the same time, a huge mass of people, united by this ritual and it did not have a clue about each other [3].

Today, the development of new media technologies and media replaced the paper in the background. The emergence of radio, film, television, computer, and today - the Internet has made the newspaper about the "legacy" type of communication. Functions that have made the once so popular newspaper - news, information, education, entertainment, now serve other media, and perform much more efficiently.

Informational society has such features as: new society that made a huge informational-technological burst; educational society; global society that doesn't know about the boundaries such as time, place and political border. Building an informational society became a strategic aim of all developed countries in the end of 1980th. Big eight countries accepted "Okinawa Charter on Global Information Society" on 22nd June, 2000. It's said there that informational-communicational technologies are one of the main factors that affect to formation of XXI century's society [4].

Information serves as a linking element of subject and object social management. Also, it's very important in preparing management actions, describing the managing decision and its' conclusion.

The American sociologist W. Dizard drew attention to the fact that information as a phenomenon - it is an international phenomenon that knows no national borders and border pillars [5].

If we look to it behalf of chief, information is "systematized type of any information, data, facts, relationships, incidents". However, it makes communication only with information that is connected with organization of management actions and implementation of them, but not all information.

Actually, state has to form scientific requirements in researches of informational problems and scientific forms, in developing and forming the safety of information system. In this case, state has to work on developing program of society, showing the state by its' positive side to public. And that is an informational politic. Materials which give rise to such feelings as love for country, patriotism and stability must be shown. Informational tools must advocate one Motherland, one state language, one national politics. Only this time, state can say that it's independent. That is the main duty of Kazakhstan today.

New culture of management is forming in Kazakhstan in XXI century. The point is: information, education, scientific prediction, social modeling. Media culture is a mediator of society and state, individual and power.

The process of informing is developing in all spheres of Kazakh society. There are made everything to upgrade state

service and administrative-managerial affairs to world standards, using new informational-communicative technologies. If Kazakhstan master new informational-communicative technologies and use it in social life, it will get to stable developing way of informational century. Electron government works hard in world political experience. Topical questions that have been told before made an influence to choose this theme. Theme is very important; it is closely connected with questions of development of management and power.

II. CONCLUSION

Thus, the social-philosophical analysis of some aspects of developing a new information society enables us to draw some conclusions. First, the information society - is a practical social reality of global and local order. Second, a number of modern science have created a strong new management concept, the information society, dynamic, especially in the leading countries of the world. Thirdly, the modern Western concept of management information society made a significant contribution to the modern science of control and are of practical importance in building the society in different countries.

REFERENCES

- [1] Toffler, A. Powershift: Knowledge, Wealth and Violence at the Edge of the 21st Century, – M: OOO "AST publishing house," 2003. – 669p.
- [2] Lull, J. Media, Communication, Culture. A Global Approach. – New York, Columbia University Press, 2000.-308p.
- [3] Erzhanova A. Nurzhanov B. Culture, Communications, Media: Almaty, 2011. - 256 p.
- [4] <http://www.russianlaw.net/law/acts/28htm>.
- [5] Tapscott D. Electron-digital society. - K.: SCHTPRESS, 2000. - 247 p.

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